

Welcome to the EXA4MIND Newsletter

Who are we? We are a Horizon Europe project that aims to build an extreme data platform that brings together large scale data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures by implementing novel automated data management and effective data staging.

EXA4MIND Plenary Meeting in Ankara

PLENARY MEETING

 MAY
6 - 7
 ANKARA

The EXA4MIND consortium gathered for its **second plenary meeting of the year** on 6–7 May 2025 in Ankara, Turkey. The event was hosted by [Middle East Technical University \(METU\)](#), with most of the technical and research partners in Ankara attending in person. The others joined virtually. Day one began with a warm welcome from METU Vice President Prof. Dr. Halil Mecit Oztop and Computer Engineering Department Chair Prof. Dr. Halit Oguztugun. Participants

then worked intensively on **finalising the content of the first training sessions EXA4MIND provides**. On day two, detailed **status reports** were presented on the [EXA4MIND application cases](#).

In addition to the plenary meeting, METU and [EuroCC Turkey](#) hosted **two EXA4MIND training sessions** on Thursday, 8 May. These sessions aimed to share knowledge and expertise with industry professionals, SMEs and students, reflecting the project's commitment to capacity building and delivering tangible results.

Discover more

Scientific publications

Annealed Winner-Takes-All for Motion Forecasting

Authors: Yihong Xu, Victor Letzelter, Mickaël Chen, Éloi Zablocki, Matthieu Cord.

Published at the [IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation \(ICRA2025\)](#).

Abstract: In autonomous driving, motion prediction aims at forecasting the future trajectories of nearby agents, helping the ego vehicle to anticipate behaviours and drive safely. A key challenge is generating a diverse set of future predictions, commonly addressed using data-driven models with Multiple Choice Learning (MCL) architectures and Winner-Takes-All (WTA) training objectives. However, these methods face initialisation sensitivity and training instabilities. Additionally, to compensate for limited performance, some approaches rely on training with a large set of hypotheses, requiring a post-selection step during inference to significantly reduce the number of predictions.

To tackle these issues, researchers take inspiration from annealed MCL, a recently introduced technique that improves the convergence properties of MCL methods through an annealed Winner-Takes-All loss (aWTA). In this paper, they demonstrate how the aWTA loss can be integrated with state-of-the-art motion forecasting models to enhance their performance using only a minimal set of hypotheses, eliminating the need for the cumbersome post-selection step. Their approach can be easily incorporated into any trajectory prediction model normally trained using WTA and yields significant improvements.

This research was made possible by EXA4MIND in the scope of the industrial/automotive application case.

[Read it on our website, here](#)

Events

EXA4MIND at the Data Spaces Symposium 2025

The [Data Spaces Symposium](#) was held from 11 to 12 March 2025 in Warsaw, Poland. As the **premier global event dedicated to the future of data spaces**, it brought together the brightest minds, leading innovators and pioneering organisations to shape a connected, data-driven world.

Two EXA4MIND consortium partners represented the project at this major event: **Kateřina Slaninová** from [IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center](#) and **Smaran Chaudhary** from the [Leibniz Supercomputing Centre](#).

Discover more

EXA4MIND presented two posters in Trieste, Italy

On 19 May, the Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire ([CECAM](#)) organised a flagship workshop entitled '[RNA modelling across scales](#)' in Trieste, Italy. **Two EXA4MIND partners** — Vojtěch Mlýnský and Pavel Banáš — **presented two posters** at the event.

Discover more

EXA4MIND returns to the ISC High Performance event

The [ISC High Performance 2025](#) event was held in Hamburg, Germany, from 10 to 13 June. It brought together **over 3,000** technology developers, providers, and users, fostering a strong sense of community. This year marked the 40th anniversary of the **world's leading forum for advancing the application of high-performance computing** in academia, government and the private sector.

As in previous years, the project coordinator, [IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center](#), represented EXA4MIND at this important event. Jan Martinovič, Kateřina Slaninová, Martin Golasowski, David Číž and Markéta Dobiašová — representing IT4Innovations and EXA4MIND — travelled to Hamburg to **promote the project at a booth** in collaboration with the [OpenWebSearch.eu project](#). The two projects are linked through the [LEXIS Platform 2](#).

The TOP500 list was also unveiled at the ISC High Performance Conference in Hamburg.

[Discover more](#)

The DataNexus Cluster

The DataNexus Cluster showcases cutting-edge solutions for extreme data challenges at Data Week 2025

[Data Week 2025](#) took place as a two-day physical event in Athens, Greece, on 27–28 May. On 28 May, [the DataNexus Cluster](#) hosted a **session entitled ‘Extreme Data-Driven Solutions and Services: Updated Perspectives and Challenges for Europe’**. This workshop showcased how five projects from the DataNexus cluster — [Graph-Massivizer](#), [NearData](#), [EMERALDS](#), [EXTRACT](#) and [EXA4MIND](#) — along with the [ExtremeXP](#) project under the AI.BIG initiative, tackle extreme data challenges to have a societal, economic, industrial and research impact. **Stephan Hachinger** from the [Leibniz Supercomputing Centre \(LRZ\)](#) represented [EXA4MIND](#) as a speaker.

[Discover more](#)

Campaign: Faces of EXA4MIND

With the **series "Faces of EXA4MIND"** we want to introduce the people who work every day to achieve our ambitious goal: Building a platform for Extreme Data that enables advanced data analytics on supercomputers and automated data management with support for integration by design with EOSC and European data spaces.

**FACES OF
EXA4MIND**

**MEET THE PEOPLE BEHIND
THE EXA4MIND PROJECT**

EXPLOITATION TASK LEADER

MARC DERQUENNES

Marc Derquennes (EURAXENT)

We present Marc Derquennes from [EURAXENT](#) and the Exploitation Task Leader of EXA4MIND.

“What makes EXA4MIND unique is its vision to unify Europe’s digital continuum by integrating pre-exascale supercomputing, cloud systems, and AI. This project will empower researchers, industries, and SMEs with seamless access to extreme data processing tools, fostering innovation and collaboration on a scale never seen before.”

[Watch his interview](#)

Upcoming events

Czech-Bavarian Supercomputing Summer School 2025

9 - 12 September 2025
Panství Dlouhá Lhota - near Prague.

EXA4MIND

A session on Supercomputing with Optimised Data Backends powered by EXA4MIND is one of the programme's highlights.

REGISTRATION DEADLINE: 10 JULY

Leibniz-Rechenzentrum
der Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften

VSB TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA

IT4INNOVATIONS NATIONAL SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER

Gefördert durch Bayerische Staatskanzlei

EXA4MIND will be part of the Czech-Bavarian Supercomputing Summer School 2025

We are happy to announce that, as part of the [Czech-Bavarian Supercomputing Summer School 2025](#) programme, students will have the opportunity to attend a session on supercomputing with optimised data backends powered by EXA4MIND. This session, which will take place on the second day, will be one of the highlights of the summer school, offering students a first-hand look at how EXA4MIND enhances supercomputing.

Important dates:

Summer school: 9–12 September.

Registration deadline: 10 July.

The summer school is organised by Stephan Hachinger from the Leibniz Supercomputing Centre, the EXA4MIND Science and Co-Design Coordinator, Jan Martinovič from IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center, the EXA4MIND Project Coordinator, along with their respective teams. It is funded by the Bavarian State Chancellery.

Registration is possible here

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